

The product may act as a *bis*-tridentate ligand. Steric factor prevents all six positions from co-ordinating to a single metal ion. Addition of a bivalent hexa-co-ordinate ion would be expected to produce the polymer shown below.

Loss of proton produces a polymer with no charge. The Zn(II) and Ni(II) complexes have been prepared in dimethylformamide solution. The infusible black powders form as precipitates. Differential thermal analysis indicates in some places no decomposition up to 400°. Insolubility of the product prevents molecular weight determination.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Naphthazarin Complex.—A solution of cupric chloride (0.53 g., 0.003 *M*), naphthazarin (0.57 g., 0.003 *M*), and triethylamine (68 g., 0.006 *M*) in 25 c.c. of absolute ethanol was refluxed for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the blue solid was removed by filtration. The complex was dried at 110°. (Found: Cu, 21.5. $Cu_3C_{20}H_{22}O_{20}$ requires Cu, 21.4%).

End group titration indicates an equivalent weight of 643. If the two end groups are phenol, a molecular weight of 1286 is indicated.

Naphthazarin Thiosemicarbazone.—Naphthazarin (3.8 g., 0.02 *M*) and thiosemicarbazide (3.6 g., 0.04 *M*) were dissolved in 30 c.c. of *NN'*-dimethylformamide, and refluxed for 2 hours. The solution was cooled to room temperature and the black precipitate of naphthazarin thiosemicarbazone was filtered. The product was washed with ethanol and dried. The sample was impure. (Found: C, 46.4; H, 2.74. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_6S_2$ requires C, 42.8; H, 3.6%).

Zinc Thiosemicarbazone of Naphthazarin.—A suspension of naphthazarin (1.9 g., 0.01 *M*) was refluxed in 30 c.c. of 1 *M*-NaOH till complete solution. Thiosemicarbazide (1.8 g., 0.02 *M*) in ethanol and powdered zinc acetate dihydrate (2.2 g., 0.02 *M*) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours. During the reflux period the deep blue solution gradually changed to black in colour and the precipitate of zinc thiosemicarbazone naphthazarin appeared. The precipitate was filtered, washed with 95% ethanol, and dried at 110°. [Found: C, 37.76; H, 2.62; Zn, 18.35 ($ZnC_{12}H_9N_6O_2S_2$)_n requires C, 36.0; H, 2.5; Zn, 16.3%].

Nickel Thiosemicarbazone of Naphthazarin.—Nickel formate (1.8 g., 0.01 *M*) in ethanol (20 c.c.) was mixed with a solution of naphthazarin (1.9 g., 0.01 *M*) and thiosemicarbazide (1.8 g., 0.02 *M*) in 20 c.c. of *NN'*-dimethylformamide. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. The precipitate of nickel thiosemicarbazone of naphthazarin was filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried at 110°. [Found: C, 37.7; H, 8.5; Ni, 11.6. ($NiC_{12}H_9O_2N_6S_2$)_n requires C, 36.9; H, 8.2; Ni, 15.0%].

Thermal Stability Measurements

Unless otherwise stated, the thermal stability of all samples was determined by differential thermal analysis. D.T.A. equipment has been constructed in this laboratory.

Samples were contained in two identical, thin wall, stainless steel cups. Aluminium oxide was used as the standard inert sample and as the diluent for the unknown. A standard sample of 2.0%g. of Al_2O_3 was balanced against a sample of 0.1 g. of the compound in 1.9 g. of Al_2O_3 .

Sample heating.—Samples were heated in an aluminium block by a 350 watt heater as shown in Fig. 1.

Maximum temperature is limited by the m.p. of the aluminium. Heating rates were varied between 8° and 2° per minute by use of a variac.

Temperature Measurement.—The differential temperature was measured by two thermopiles of four, iron-constantan thermocouples inside a thin-wall capillary. Absolute temperature was measured by a single iron-constantan thermocouple placed in the sample. The thermocouple was protected by a thin-wall glass capillary. The system was standardised against the crystal structure change of NH_4Cl , which occurs at 184.3° .

Temperature Recorder.—Both absolute and differential temperatures were recorded by a Brown, 2-point, automatic recording potentiometer. The absolute scale was extended by inclusion of a "buck out" potential from a Rubicon Co. potentiometer.

Differential temperature of 0.02° may be determined. Absolute temperature may be determined to 0.5° .

Sample Atmosphere.—No attempt was made to control the atmosphere above the sample. Access to the air was restricted, however, by the Al_2O_3 diluent and the aluminium cover.

Differential Plots.—The decomposition peaks are very broad, usually extended for several minutes. Maximum stability was taken as the point of initial rise of differential plot. Peak maxima usually occurred at a temperature approximately 10° higher than the initial break.

Decomposition Point.—Decomposition point of the compounds, as recorded by the D.T.A. set up described above, are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Point of D.T. change.
1.	Copper naphthazarin complex	355°
2.	Naphthazarin thiosemicarbazone	320°
3.	Zinc thiosemicarbazone of naphthazarin	450°
4.	Nickel thiosemicarbazone of naphthazarin	400°

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